

A Study on the Solute-Solute and Solute-Solvent Interactions of some Tetraalkylammonium Perchlorates in Aqueous Binary Mixtures of 2-Methoxyethanol from their Partial Molar Volume Data

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The apparent molar volumes of four symmetrical tetraalkylammonium perchlorates (Me_4NClO_4 , Et_4NClO_4 , Pr_4NClO_4 and Bu_4NClO_4) have been determined in 2-methoxyethanol (ME) + water mixtures containing 20, 40, 60 and 80 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol at 25°. The apparent molar volumes are extrapolated to zero concentration to obtain the limiting values at infinite dilution. Ionic limiting partial molar volumes have been estimated using the extrapolation method. Ion-ion interactions are found to be very weak but increase with increasing amount of 2-methoxyethanol in the solvent mixtures. The results have been explained on the basis of the electrostriction effect of the perchlorate ion and the hydrophobic and size effects of the tetraalkylammonium ions.

The volumetric behaviour of solutes has been proved to be very useful in elucidating the various interactions occurring in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions¹. Studies on the apparent and partial molar volumes of electrolytes have been used to examine the ion-ion, ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions². The apparent and partial molar volumes of tetraalkylammonium salts have been investigated rather extensively in aqueous^{3,4} and non-aqueous solvents⁵⁻⁷, but such measurements are relatively scarce in organic solvent + water binary systems⁸. In the present work, we have carried out a systematic study on the apparent and partial molar volumes of tetraalkylammonium perchlorates, R_4NClO_4 (R = methyl to butyl) in 2-methoxyethanol (ME) + water mixtures containing 20, 40, 60 and 80 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol at 25°.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) were calculated from the densities of the solution using equation (1),

$$\phi_v = M / \rho_0 - 1000 (\rho - \rho_0) / c \rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where c is the molarity of the electrolyte solution, M the molecular weight of the solute and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and solvent respectively. The limiting apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 (equal to the partial molar volumes at infinite dilution \bar{V}_2^0) were obtained by least-squares fitting of the ϕ_v values to the equation,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* \sqrt{c} \quad (2)$$

where S_v^* is the experimental slope. The plots of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} were linear in all cases, and from the intercept and slope one can obtain the values of ϕ_v^0 ($= \bar{V}_2^0$) and S_v^* respectively. The values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* are given in Table 1.

The S_v^* values for all the electrolytes are very small and increase with the concentration of 2-methoxyethanol in the solvent mixtures, thereby suggesting that the ion-ion interactions are very small in different 2-methoxy-

ethanol + water mixtures and that these interactions increase on the addition of 2-methoxyethanol. Table 1 shows that the limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) are large and positive, and the values increase with increasing size of the cations. This is in agreement with earlier findings in several non-aqueous solvents as well as in water and heavy

TABLE 1—LIMITING APPARENT MOLAR VOLUMES AND EXPERIMENTAL SLOPES OF TETRAALKYLAMMONIUM PERCHLORATES IN 2-METHOXYETHANOL (ME) + WATER MIXTURES (w/w) AT 25°

Electrolyte	0% ME ^a	20% ME 40% ME 60%ME 80% ME			
		ϕ_v^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
Me_4NClO_4	134.35	132.04	129.94	128.65	131.01
Et_4NClO_4	193.65	188.41	184.90	182.50	182.12
Pr_4NClO_4	259.25	250.66	246.00	253.93	233.61
Bu_4NClO_4	320.35	312.59	306.91	317.54	296.96
		S_v^* (cm ³ l ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})			
Me_4NClO_4		0.66	0.78	1.05	1.23
Et_4NClO_4		0.45	0.59	0.80	1.01
Pr_4NClO_4		0.36	0.46	0.65	0.89
Bu_4NClO_4		0.19	0.31	0.44	0.56

^aRef. 2.

water^{6,7}. The large ϕ_v^0 values reveal that the solute-solvent interactions are strong in this medium.

The calculation of the limiting ionic partial molar volumes has been done following the method suggested by Conway *et al.*³. According to this procedure, the \bar{V}_2^0 values of the tetraalkylammonium perchlorates were plotted against the formula weight of the corresponding tetraalkylammonium ions. An excellent linear relationship was observed in all cases for these electrolytes in the various 2-methoxyethanol + water mixtures. The \bar{V}_{ion}^0 values of tetraalkylammonium and perchlorate ions thus obtained are presented in Table 2. The ionic partial molar volume of the perchlorate ion as a function of solvent composition (Table 2) shows a minimum at 60 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol. This may be attributed to the maximum electrostriction effect of the perchlorate ion at this composition. A perusal of

the ionic limiting partial molar volumes of the cations as a function of solvent composition reveals that all the cations show a minimum at 20 mass% and a maximum at 60 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol. The similarity in the variation of the single-ion values as a function of the solvent composition for all the cations suggests that the same effects are operating in all the cases. To analyse these observations, one must realise that they represent the combined effects of cation and anion. The minimum at 60 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol for the perchlorate ion is due to the electrostriction effect of the anion and this effect is opposed by the hydrophobic and size effects of the tetraammonium cations, which is characterised by a maximum at the same solvent composition. The resulting balance between these two effects is demonstrated by the variation of the limiting partial molar volumes of the total electrolyte as a function of solvent composition. In case of tetramethyl-ammonium perchlorate a minimum is observed at 60 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol, indicating that the electrostriction effect of the perchlorate ion predominates over the small hydrophobic and size effects of the tetramethylammonium cation. However, in tetraethylammonium salt we find no minimum at 60 mass% of the organic cosolvent, suggesting that the perchlorate ion electrostriction effect is more or less compensated by the hydrophobic and size effects of the cation. The electrostriction effect of the anion is eventually outweighed by the hydrophobic and size effects in tetrapropyl- and tetrabutylammonium salts which is mani-

distilled. The purified water had a specific conductance of less than 1×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹ at 25°. The mixed solvents were prepared by mixing accurately the requisite amounts of water and 2-methoxyethanol (by weights). Freshly distilled solvents were always used for preparing the experimental solutions. Tetraalkylammonium perchlorates were of Fluka purum or puriss grade. All the salts were recrystallised from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at 70° for 24 h.

A stock solution for each salt was prepared by weight and working solutions were obtained by weight-dilution. The conversion of the molality into molarity was done by using the density values. The densities were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of about 25 cm³ and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 1 mm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 25° with double-distilled water. Measurements were made in a water-bath maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.01^\circ$) by means of a mercury-in-glass thermoregulator and the absolute temperature was determined by a calibrated platinum resistance thermometer and Muller bridge. The precision of the density measurements was always greater than $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³.

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TABLE 2--IONIC LIMITING PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUMES IN 2-METHOXYETHANOL (ME) + WATER MIXTURES (w/w) AT 25°

Ion	0% ME ^a	20% ME	40% ME	60% ME	80% ME
Me ₄ N ⁺	83.40	81.51	80.04	88.04	75.08
Et ₄ N ⁺	142.70	137.88	135.00	141.89	126.19
Pr ₄ N ⁺	208.30	200.13	196.10	213.29	177.68
Bu ₄ N ⁺	269.40	262.06	257.01	276.93	241.03
ClO ₄ ⁻	50.95	50.53	49.90	40.93	55.93

^aRef. 2.

fested by the pronounced maxima at 60 mass% of 2-methoxyethanol for both these electrolytes.

Experimental

2-Methoxyethanol (G. R., E. Merck) was distilled twice in an all-glass distillation set before use and the middle fraction collected. The purified solvent had a density of 0.96002 g cm⁻³, and a coefficient of viscosity of 1.5414 mPa s at 25° and these values compare well with the literature values, e.g., 0.96016 g cm⁻³ and 1.5430 mPa s respectively⁹. Water was first deionised and then distilled using alkaline KMnO₄ solution. The distillate was then finally